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A Study on Challenges and Opportunities in Speech Recognition Technique

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Abstract

This is the paper that provides brief research on the automatic speech recognition technology and it also provides the achievements in this field from the past 60 years. After a strong research and study in this span the technology has acquired its accuracy in this field. This particular paper summarises the opportunities and challenges in this field.

Key words: Automatic Speech Recognition, research, 60 years, technology, opportunities, challenges.

Introduction

Speech recognition is a computer technology that develops methods and techniques that enable the translation of the spoken language by any person into text by computers. It is also called as “Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)”, “Computer Speech Recognition” or “Speech To Text (STT)”. It includes knowledge and research in the computer science and electrical engineering fields,

Some speech recognition techniques require training for the person to read the text into the system and some does not require training this system analyses the person’s specific voice and uses it as the fine-tuning for recognition of the person’s voice and which results in increased accuracy. The systems that do not require training for input of text into computer is called as “speaker independent systems” and the technique which require training are called as “speaker dependent”.

Speech recognition is used in many ways, it is used as voice dialling such as “call home”, call routing such as “I would like to make a collect call”, simple data entry such as “entering a credit card number”, etc

The term speech recognition refers to the recognition or identification of speech of the speaker. Recognizing the speaker can make the task of translating speech into the systems that have been

trained on a specific person's voice easier or it can be used to verify the identity of the speaker as the part of security program. From the technology point of view, speech recognition has a very long history with several developments. The speech recognition players are Google, Microsoft, IBM, Apple, Amazon, etc.

Methodology

Secondary sources; Journals; Articles and Google

The Objective of the paper

- To study the opportunities in speech recognition technique
- To find out the achievements in speech recognition technique till date
- To study the challenges in this field

History

Early work

- 1952- three bell labs researchers: Stephen Balashek, R. Biddulph, K.H. Davis, built a system Called Aundrey.
- The 1950s- in this era technology was limited to single-speaker systems with vocabularies of around ten words.
- 1960- Gunnar Fant developed the source filter model of speech production and published
- The 1960s- The first person to take on continuous speech recognition as a graduate student at Stanford University was Raj Reddy.

Practical speech recognition

- The 1990s- The first introduction of commercially successful speech recognition technology
- 1990- Two of the earliest products were Dragon Dictate, a consumer product released
- 1987- recognizer from Kurzweil Applied Intelligence released
- 1992- AT&T deployed the Voice Recognition Call Processing service
- 1992- The Sphinx-II system was the first to do speaker-independent, large vocabulary, continuous speech recognition and it had the best performance in DARPA's evaluation.
- 1993- Huang went on to investigate the speech recognition group at Microsoft
- 1992- Raj Reddy's student Kai-Fu Lee joined Apple where, he helped develop a speech interface prototype for the Apple computer known as Casper.

Modern systems

In the early 2000s, speech recognition was still dominated by traditional approaches such as Hidden Markov models combined with feedforward artificial neural networks.

Around 2007- LSTM trained by Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) started to outperform traditional speech recognition in applications.

In 2015- Google's speech recognition reportedly experienced a dramatic performance jump of 49% through CTC-trained LSTM, which is now available through google voice to all smartphone users.

Models, methods, and algorithms

Both the Acoustic modeling and the Language modeling are important for the modern statistics-based speech recognition model. Hidden Markov models are mostly used in many systems. Language modeling is also used in other natural language processing applications.

Hidden Markov models-the main reason why these HMMs are used because they can be trained automatically and are very simple and Easy to use.

Dynamic time warping (DTW)-based speech recognition

Dynamic time warping is a technique which was used from long ago and, it is now replaced by the Hidden Markov model

Dynamic Time warping is a technique used to measure the similarity between the two series that may be different in time and speed. Moreover, any data that could be turned into a linear representation can be analyzed with Dynamic Time Warping.

Automatic speech recognition is a very well-known technology that can meet different speaking speeds. It is a technology which finds the match between two given sequences with some restrictions.

The modern and very used speech recognition techniques were based on the Hidden Markov model. These models are statistical models which provide a sequence of symbols or quantities. HMMs are used in speech recognition technology because a speech signal could be easily viewed as a piecewise stationary or a short-term stationary.

Neural networks

These methods came as an attractive acoustic modeling approach in Automatic Speech Recognition in the late 1980s.

Neural networks in contrast between the Hidden Markov Model makes no assumptions about the feature statistical properties, and it also has many qualities that make them attractive speech recognition models.

End-to-end automatic speech recognition

From 2014, there had been much research work done in end-to-end automatic speech recognition technique. The traditional technique requires training for pronunciation and learning model. End-to-end models all together learn the components of the speech recognizer.

Opportunities

In-car systems

Speech recognition techniques were most widely used in the car systems. These are manually operated by fingers in the steering wheel which enables the speech recognition system, and this is conveyed to the driver by audio signals by the system and, the system with its listening window will accept the speech input from the drivers for recognition.

Using this technique, the driver can easily attend the phone calls, select or play music from a connectable smartphone or device. The voice recognition may vary from the car make and the car model. And some of the modern cars allow the recognition by the normally spoken language which does not require a person to memorize or use fixed commands.

Health care

Medical documentation

Speech recognition is most widely used in the medical field also. It is used in two ways namely front end or back-end of medical documentation procedure. Front-end speech recognition is where the person dictates the report into the speech-recognition engine and, the words are displayed as they were spoken. The dictator is responsible for editing and signing the document.

Back-end speech recognition is where the person dictates into the digital dictation system, the voice is recognized by the system and the system provides the original voice file to the editor. This is the system which is in use currently.

Military

High-performance fighter aircraft

Speech recognition is also most widely used in the medical fields also. very strong effects have been put in the last ten years to the test of speech recognition in the fighter aircraft.in many programmes held by the UK, the US the speech recognition technique has been very successfully operated in the fighter aircrafts. In applications such as setting radio frequencies, commanding an autopilot system, etc.

Helicopters

The speech recognition technique is widely used in helicopters many problems faced by helicopters such as problem in acquiring accuracy under stress and high noise in helicopter environment. Strong research and efforts are put in the last ten years to solve these problems using the speech recognition technology in the helicopters by the Army Avionics Research and Development Activity (AVRADA) and by the Royal Aerospace Establishment (RAE) in the UK.

Training air traffic controllers

The speech recognition technique used in training for air traffic controllers (ATC) acts as the best example for this technology. Many ATC training systems currently require a person to act as a “pseudo-pilot”.

Many countries are successfully using this speech recognition technique in different fields.

Usage in education and daily life

Speech recognition is also used in daily life of a person. A person in Google can speak what ever he wants to search, and Google will give him the details without typing any input in keyboard.

Students who are blind or have very low vision can benefit of using the technology to convey words and then hear the computer recite them, as well as use a computer by commanding with their voice, instead of having to look at the screen and keyboard.

The handicap students or the children those who are suffering from injuries, by using this technology of speech recognition do not have to worry about the handwriting, typing, etc. they can also search anything in google or internet without the requirement of operating the mouse and keyboard.

This technology is very useful for the persons with physical disabilities. This technology was used by the famous scientist Stephen Hawkins.

Speech recognition is the best technology for the people with disabilities and students also. People with disabilities

Mr. Stephen Hawkins

The speech recognition technique is a very help full technology for the persons who are disabled. The persons who are deaf or dumb, speech recognition technique is used to automatically generate a conversation such as classrooms, lectures etc.

This is the technology which is very useful for those who are physically disabled and for those people who cannot use their hands for writing or typing etc. the person only need to speak what he wants to search or convey, and computer does everything for them using speech recognition technology.

The major challenges faced by speech recognition technology

As this technology is a very new concept to the people it is difficult for them to adapt to the technology.

As many users do not know to use the technology it is difficult for them to use it.

It is not easy to make all the people know the use of this technology. It might also take much time and money to do this process of training the people.

As people do not study the Manuel of usage of the technology they do not know the proper use of the technology.

Sometimes due to lack of knowledge of what technology does it might lead to misuse the technology.

There are lots of synonyms in the English grammar the computer may wrongly recognise the word. Normally sometimes humans themselves misunderstand or misinterpret.

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